

Paper 18

A STUDY ON THE USE OF MEDICINAL PLANTS IN THE AREA OF NEUROPSYCHIATRY AND NEUROLOGY FOR A SUSTAINABLE MENTAL HEALTH

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: The current study set out to identify therapeutic plants with psychoactive qualities that were being utilized to treat neuropsychiatric disorders in patients with nervous system diseases as well as general and complex neuropsychiatric disorders.

Objective: The core or base objective of this study is to identify plant originated psychoactive molecules or psychotropic actives and its relation in the area of neuropsychiatric or neurologic treatment.

Design/Methodology/Approach: The majority of the material utilized to construct the study is secondary and comes from a variety of sources, including clinical literature, journals, websites, etc. Additionally, primary data has been employed to boost the paper's correctness and dependability. Clinical psychopathologists, cardiologists, neuropsychologists, and behavioral medicine experts provided the primary data. To prevent any mistakes and inaccuracies, a comprehensive, rigorous clinical examination of the data has been performed using all of these databases

Findings/ Results: The findings list 66 plant species that are utilized to treat neuropsychiatric disorders. The primary plant components utilized were roots (36.2%) and leaves (29%) These components, either alone or in combination, were utilized to make medications primarily through the decoction and trituration processes. Drinks, external treatments, and fumigation were all used to provide remedies. This research suggests that local conventional medicine in many regions of the world has a thorough understanding of neuropsychiatric diseases. The therapeutic treatments recommended in this article are a genuine effort to combat neurological and mental illnesses. Future research on antipsychotic or neuroprotective chemicals may utilize identified plants.

Originality and value: To cover the relevant study issue and increase the validity and reliability of the material, a thorough analysis and interpretation have been done. A fresh approach is used to spread knowledge regarding the relationship between medicinal plants and the human mind.

Paper type: Secondary Clinical Report Analysis/ Interpretive

Keywords: Sustainable mental health, Medicinal plants, Neuropsychiatric disorders, Phytochemicals, Phytotherapies

1. INTRODUCTION:

The use of medicinal plants in conventional therapy is expanding and diversifying in modern times. These shrubs were a priceless gift to humanity as a whole and were especially crucial for the survival and healthcare of the people in developing nations [1]. They are essential resources for the vast majority of rural African populations, who use them to provide for their primary healthcare in more than 80% of cases [2]. The World Health Organization (WHO) classifies neuropsychiatric disorders as a group of "mental health problems" that are marked by abnormalities in thought, emotion, behavior, and interpersonal relationships. These pathologies place limitations on the affected person and on those in their circle. Genetic, social, environmental, and psychotropic drug factors are the main causes of these disorders. The burden of global morbidity, which includes mental and neurological disorders, is 13%. Neuropsychiatric disorders are a lifelong condition that affect between 13% and 49% of the world's population. All racial, gender, and age categories of people are affected by these pathologies [3]. One of the most widespread neurological disorders is epilepsy. It affects more than 50 million people worldwide, with 80% of them living in developing nations. Approximately 75% of patients in Africa do not receive the appropriate care, which is a high prevalence. The stigmatization of sick people, who are frequently marginalized, is a result of misconceptions about neuropsychiatric diseases [4]. In contemporary medicine, a range of organic or synthetic psychoactive molecules, including neuroleptics, antidepressants, and anxiolytics, are used to treat these pathologies, in particular epilepsy, schizophrenia, and other psychotic disorders. But for African populations living in rural areas, these contemporary treatments are prohibitively expensive, complicated, and unavailable [5]. Numerous of these psychedelic molecules are derived from plants, which may support the use of plants in African/Indian traditional medicine to cure neuropsychiatric illnesses. The species of plants used for this therapy practice have also been the subject of numerous studies. The specific use of plants in Burkina Faso to treat disorders of the nervous system has received little attention from research, though. These abnormalities were commonly discussed in psychiatric consultations in the Hauts Bassins region. The traditional treatment of these pathologies is only mentioned in other parallel studies, with the exception of Millogo's group's work on "epilepsy and conventional medicine in Bobo-Dioulasso" [6]. In the Hauts Bassins province of Burkina Faso and some rural and tribal parts in India, medicinal plants are used to treat neuropsychiatric disorders. The purpose of the current study is to describe these plants. It was required to record the medicinal plants, medical procedures, and traditional healers used to treat neurological and psychic disorders.

2. RELATED WORKS:

Recent *in vitro* assays have demonstrated that numerous plants that are consumed or used in conventional medicine may be mutagenic. Thus, it is crucial to support claims made about the efficacy and safety of such uses by conducting scientific evaluations of herbal medicine and medicinal plants. Ten shrubs in use in South African traditional medicine were chosen after an examination of the ethnobotanical literature that was available [7]. These species included the *Albizia adianthifolia*, *Combretum Krauss*, *Ficus sur*, *Prunus Africana*, *Salix mucronata*, *Terminalia sericea*, and *Trichilia dracaena*. The *Acacia* biological subspecies *kraussiana* and *Acacia sieberiana* were also included. With the exception of *Albizia adianthifolia*, *Faidherbia albida*, *Terminalia sericea*, and *Prunus Africana*, plant parts including leaves, roots, and bark were taken from each of the chosen trees and extracted using ethyl acetate, ethanol, and water

independently to ensure the separation of compounds over a wide range of polarities [8]. The extracts (a total of 78) were examined for their prospective mutagenic effects using the Ames test as well as for their antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory (COX-1 as well as COX-2), and antiacetylcholinesterase activities [9]. With the aid of the disc-diffusion & microdilution assays, antibacterial activity was discovered. The extracts were evaluated against Gram-positive bacteria like *E. coli* and *Klebsiella pneumonia* as well as Gram-negative bacteria like *B. subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Micrococcus luteus* [10]. Out of the 111 plant extracts from 78 different species that were tested, 84% had activity against Gram-positive bacteria.

3. OBJECTIVES:

This paper is prepared to through some lights on the topic of using medicinal plants or other shrubs for treating neuropsychological or any other central nervous system disorders. Whenever a layman here about the word 'medicinal plant' or 'traditional medicine', it is common to think about India or especially world renowned and scientific conventional treatment called Ayurveda. Some African countries are also blessed with some rare species of medicinal plants which can be utilized to treat some cognitive and neurodegenerative disorders. The main object of this paper is to identify such medicinal plants or medicinal shrubs and its uses in the area of neurodegenerative disorders and neuropsychiatric treatments. The main objectives of this paper are listed below:

1. To tabulate different medicinal plants
2. To identify different types of natural medicinal molecules contained in medicinal plants
3. To understand the role of phytochemicals to treat neurological and neuropsychological disorder.

4. METHODOLOGY:

The foundation of this study is secondary data. The final outcome and conclusion were reached after a thorough, scientific analysis. Although the paper is premised on secondary data, the author's own clinical experience provided some additional context that helped to improve the data's accuracy. A professional opinion has been obtained in order to maintain and improve the paper's reliability and validity. In this regard, a systematic analysis of more than fifty journal papers, both published and unpublished, has been conducted.

5. COMMON PLANT SPECIES USED IN THE CONVENTIONAL TREATMENT SYSTEM:

A total of 66 plant species, including 51 trees and 15 herbaceous species, were found to be effective in the treatment of psychiatric and neurological disorders. They belonged to 32 families and 56 genera (Table 1) [11]. With four species each, the genera *Acacia* and *Ficus* were the most well-represented. *Mimosaceae* (8 genera), *Fabaceae* (5 species), and *Rubiaceae* were the three families with the most species (5 species). The most popular of these plants are listed in Table 2 [12]. The majority of traditional healers reported using *Securidaca long pedunculate* (40.23%), *Calotropis Procera* (20.75%), *Khaya senegalensis* (30.55%), *Allium sativum* (20.55%), *Daniella Oliveri* (15%), and *Annona senegalensis* (20%) frequently (TH). Among the oldest, *Datura innoxia* and *Zanthoxylum zanthoxylodes* were used. Six species were used to treat the primary diseases targeted: *S. long pedunculate*, *C. procera*, *K. senegalensis*, *A. senegalensis*,

Diospyros mespiliformis, and *Guiera Senegalensis*. The majority of the plants were utilized either on their own or in combination with other plants [13].

6. MEDICINAL PLANTS AND NEUROPSYCHIATRIC TREATMENTS:

Table 3 lists illnesses or regroupings of illnesses that were treated by traditional healers (TH) [14]. According to these findings, the most commonly treated conditions were hallucinations or loss of consciousness, preceded by epilepsy, mental illnesses, witchcraft, and evils connected to charm [15]. Other conditions, like insomnia and nervous diseases, are also treated in addition to such target pathologies. Each of the listed disorders is treated by multiple plant species. So, 37 plants were utilized to treat hallucinations or loss of consciousness, 32 to treat mental illnesses, 31 to combat epilepsy, and 25 to treat ailments brought on by charm or witchcraft [16]. Table 1 lists illnesses or regroupings of illnesses that were treated by traditional healers (TH).

Name	Number of Plants Used
Epilepsy	31
Hallucination or Consciousness loss	37
Insomnia	2
Mental disorders or Madness	32
Nerves diseases	1
Witchcraft or Charm diseases	25

7. DISCUSSION:

The three neuropsychiatric conditions that are most frequently treated by traditional healers are hallucinations, seizure disorders, and psychiatric illnesses, respectively (TH) [17], [18], [19]. These findings are consistent with those of other studies, which showed that many African nations as well as India's traditional medicine are aware of and treat these pathologies. A total of 66 plant species from various families that are utilized to treat neuropsychiatric diseases were reported. The outcome confirms TH's understanding of the local plant variety and its medicinal benefits. Previous research with similar findings revealed that Burkinabe communities were well recognized to benefit from the finest aspects of biodiversity in traditional medicine. The majority (87%) of plants found are ligneous. The primary species employed were *S. long pedunculata*, *C. procera*, *K. senegalensis*, *A. sativum*, *D. Oliveri*, and *A. senegalensis*; earlier TH exclusively used *D. innoxia* and *Z. zanthoxyloides* [20]. They were mentioned as plant species that were used in other African nations to treat neuropsychiatric diseases. Numerous writers claim that all of these plants include phytochemicals that have an impact on the neurological system. They include cardiac glycosides, alkaloids, terpenoids, steroids, flavonoids, tannins, and saponins (Table 4) [21]. The primary bioactive components of medicinal plants were thought to be these chemical components. Alkaloids like -amyrin and -amyrin are found in the root bark of *C. procera*, which is used to cure anxiety, epilepsy, and lunacy. Cardenolides like calactin, calotoxin, calotropin, and uscharin are found in the leaf and latex of the plant [22]. The historic

usage of this plant may be a result of its chemical composition. Additionally, *C. procera* extracts were said to have potent analgesic and anticonvulsant effects [23], [24], [25]. The anticholinergic properties of tropical alkaloids like scopolamine, atropine, and hyoscyamine found in *D. innoxia* are well documented. As cholinergic antagonists, they work. Antimuscarinic scopolamine is a common analgesic and muscle relaxant [24]. The use of *Datura* in the treatment of mental illnesses may be partially explained by the anticholinergic and antimuscarinic actions of these substances. The spinal cord is stimulated by securidine, an alkaloid derived from *S. long pedunculate* root. It affected the autonomic nervous system's functionality when used at a non-toxic dosage [26], [27], [28]. Some flavonoids have been shown to have neuroprotective and anti-anxiety properties, and they have a high affinity for the GABAA receptors. For instance, 2S(-)-hesperidin possesses sedative and sleep-inducing characteristics, while 6-methylapigenin is a benzodiazepine binding site ligand [29], [30], [31]. The cerebral ischemia lesion was greatly reduced by quercetin. While apigenin was extracted from *S. long pedunculate* and Quercetin was found in the majority of the plants described in this study, hesperidin was found in *C. aurantifolia* and *Z. zanthoxylodes* (Table 4) [32], [34]. These bioactive substances could be responsible for plants' success in treating neuropsychiatric conditions. These substances have an impact on the brain in a variety of ways, one of which is by controlling the activity of neurotransmitters [35]. The positive benefits of these botanicals do not, however, mask their negative consequences. They do indeed also have cardiotoxic and cytotoxic effects. Securinine acts similarly to strychnine in the 5-30 g/kg range, triggering spasms and respiratory arrest death [36]. Tropic alkaloids have the potential to be neurotoxic. Therefore, it is important to encourage the responsible use of these plants.

8. RESULTS:

The findings of the indigenous plants survey support earlier phytochemical investigations on the traditional applications of the plants listed and the presence of their psychotropic components. Indeed, the most well-known compounds with psychedelic characteristics are alkaloids. Similar claims were made about certain flavonoids, steroids, and terpenoids having a psychedelic impact. These chemical components get in the way and interfere with neurotransmitter functions. They promote, impede, or obstruct neurotransmitter release, reception, or removal. The primary herbs are shown to have anticonvulsant, anxiolytic, antispasmodic, antinociceptive, analgesic, or sedative characteristics by pharmacological research. This finding could attest to the existence of psychotropic substances in these plants.

9. CONCLUSION:

His research allowed for the reporting of 66 plant species from 51 genera and 32 families that are utilized to treat neuropsychiatric illnesses. The most often employed organs were roots and leaves, and the two main methods for making drugs were decoction and trituration. The majority of the time, medications was given orally. The found plants were said to have chemical components that might support such psychotropic characteristics. The traditional treatments mentioned in this study have significant value in the treatment of neuropsychiatric diseases. The identification of these plants' psychoactive chemicals and their modes of action for the therapy of neuropsychiatric diseases would therefore require more investigation.

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